

Synthesis and Fungicidal Activity of Arylidene Acetoacet Hydrazides

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1-Aryl-2-pyrazolin-5-ones and 4-arylidene-2-pyrazolin-5-ones on treatment with hydrazine hydrate produce respectively phenyl hydrazone of acetoacet hydrazide and arylidene derivative of above. A derivative of acetoacet hydrazide with a 5-pyrazolone ring as substituent on its active methylene carbon has been produced by two methods, both involving Michael addition of a reactive methylene derivative to a $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated carbonyl compound. 50 compounds thus prepared have been screened for their antifungal activity against the rice blast pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae* and brown leaf spot pathogen *Helminthosporium oryzae*.

With few exceptions, all these compounds exhibit significant antifungal activity against these two pathogens. The fungicidal activity of most of these compounds is comparable with the standard fungicides like *o*-Ethyl-S, S-diphenyl phosphorodithioate (Hinosan 50%) EC, MBC 50% WP, Difolatan 50% WP and Derosal 60% WP.

THIS is in continuation to our earlier work on heterocyclic fungicides¹⁻⁷. It has been observed that 5-pyrazolone and its mono-arylidene derivatives⁸ possess significant fungicidal activity against the rice blast pathogen *Pyricularia Oryzae* and brown leaf spot pathogen *Helminthosporium Oryzae*. When treated with hydrazine hydrate, 4-arylidene derivatives of 5-pyrazolone and the parent pyrazolone, there is ring opening and addition resulting in the formation of hydrazides. These hydrazides were found to be more active than the 4-arylidene derivatives and the parent pyrazolone itself. 24 arylidene derivatives of phenyl hydrazone of acetoacet hydrazide were prepared. The enhanced fungicidal activity of these hydrazides and the significant fungicidal activity of 5-pyrazolones encouraged us to combine both the fungicidal active moieties in one molecule. A derivative of acetoacet hydrazide 'A' with a 5-pyrazolone ring as substituent on its active methylene carbon has been produced by two methods both involving Michael addition of a reactive methylene derivative to a $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated carbonyl compound.

The identity of the two products obtained by two different methods was confirmed from m.m.p. and super imposition of IR absorption spectrum. 24 such addition products were prepared. It was observed that the Michael addition products displayed more fungicidal activity than the starting materials.

All the compounds prepared during the present investigation were screened for their antifungal activity against the rice blast pathogen *P. oryzae* and brown leaf spot pathogen *H. oryzae* by the standard method⁹, using spore germination tests at

various concentrations. Considering the fungicidal activity of the two compounds phenyl hydrazone of acetoacet hydrazide and hydrazone of acetoacet hydrazide (Sl. No. 1 and 2) (Table 1), it was observed that both these two compounds exhibit significant antifungal activity against the pathogens *P. oryzae* and *H. oryzae*.

Out of the 24 arylidene derivatives of the phenyl hydrazone of acetoacet hydrazide, it was seen that

TABLE-1

Sl. No.	Nature of 'R'	M.P. in °C	%C Found (Reqd.)	%H Found (Reqd.)	%N Found (Reqd.)	% of germination inhibition at 1000 ppm concentration.	
						<i>P. oryzae</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>
1.	C ₆ H ₅	219	58.17 (58.25)	6.81 (6.90)	27.23 (27.18)	92	80
2.	H	226	36.87 (36.90)	7.72 (7.69)	43.15 (43.15)	87	76

one compound (Sl. No. 18) (Table 2) was ineffective against the pathogen *P. oryzae* and 4 compounds (Sl. No. 18, 19, 22 and 23) did not exhibit significant activity against the pathogen *H. oryzae*. The remaining compounds showed encouraging antifungal activity against these two pathogens. Compounds (Sl. No. 6, 9 and 13) inhibited 100% spore germination of the pathogen *P. oryzae* at 1000 ppm concentration.

In case of the 24 Michael addition products, 2 compounds (Sl. No. 42 and 45) (Table 3) did not exhibit significant antifungal activity against the pathogen *P. oryzae* and 6 compounds (Sl. No. 37, 39, 42, 44, 45 and 48) did not show antifungal activity against the pathogen *H. oryzae*. The remaining compounds showed pronounced fungicidal activity against these two pathogens. Further it was observed that compounds (Sl. No. 27, 30, 32, and 33) exhibit 100% spore germination inhibition of the pathogen *P. oryzae* at 1000 ppm concentration and compound (Sl. No. 30) inhibited 100% spore germination of the pathogen *H. oryzae* at 1000 ppm concentration. It was seen that in general the compounds showed higher germination inhibition in case of the pathogen *P. oryzae* and comparatively less inhibition against the pathogen *H. Oryzae*. The fungicidal activities of the prepared compounds were compared with standard fungicides like *o*-Ethyl-S, S-diphenyl phosphorodithioate (Hinosan 50%) EC, MBC 50% WP, Difolatan 50% WP and Derosal 60% WP which inhibited 95, 88, 98, 87% of spore germination of the pathogen *P. oryzae* at 1000 ppm concentration. It was seen that 16 compounds (Sl. No. 1, 2, 6, 8-10, 13, 15, 21, 27, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34 and 48) inhibited spore germination in the same range as the above standard fungicides and hence may be used as commercial fungicides.

Experimental

Preparation of Phenyl hydrazone of acetoacet hydrazide :

1-Ph-3-Me-2-pyrazolin-5-one (2 g) was mixed with 80% hydrazine hydrate (1.8 g). The resulting

mixture was refluxed over a small flame for 4 hrs. It was then kept for overnight. A yellowish needle-shaped compound was settled at the bottom of the flask. On crystallisation from abs. alcohol, yellowish needle-shaped crystals were obtained, m.p. 219°, yield 75%. The compound is soluble in 10% sodium hydroxide and gives colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

Preparation of benzylidene derivative of phenyl hydrazone of acetoacet hydrazide :

1-Ph-3-Me-4-benzylidene-5-pyrazolone (2 g) was mixed with 80% hydrazine hydrate (1.5 g). The resulting mixture was refluxed over a small flame for 4 hrs. It was then kept overnight. Yellowish compound was obtained. On crystallisation from abs. alcohol, yellowish needle-shaped crystals were obtained, m.p. 162°, yield 80%. The product is insoluble in 10% sodium hydroxide and gives no colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

Preparation of the Michael addition product of Benzylidene derivative of phenyl hydrazone of acetoacet hydrazide and 1-Ph-3-Me-2-pyrazolin-5-one :

Method I :

Benzylidene derivative of phenyl hydrazone of acetoacet hydrazide (1 g) was dissolved in abs. alcohol (5 ml). To it 1-Ph-3-Me-2-pyrazolin-5-one (0.6 g) dissolved in 10% sodium hydroxide (6 ml) was added, at room temperature. Immediate precipitation of a white compound occurred. On crystallisation from abs. alcohol, white needle-shaped crystals were obtained, m.p. 157°, yield 80%.

The product is soluble in 10% sodium hydroxide and gives colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

Method II :

Phenyl hydrazone of acetoacet hydrazide (1 g) was dissolved in 10% sodium hydroxide (5 ml). To it 1-Ph-3-Me-4-benzylidene-5-pyrazolone (1.2 g) dissolved in abs. alcohol (5 ml) was added at room

TABLE-2

Sl. No.	Nature of R	Nature of R'	M.P. °C	%C Found (Reqd.)	%H Found (Reqd.)	%N Found (Reqd.)	% of germination inhibition at 1000 ppm conc.	
							<i>P. oryzae</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>
3.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	162	69.21 (69.38)	6.27 (6.12)	19.02 (19.04)	68	65
4.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (o)	149	60.27 (60.17)	5.13 (5.01)	20.54 (20.64)	77	67
5.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (m)	151	60.20 (60.17)	5.09 (5.01)	20.58 (20.64)	60	64
6.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (p)	175	60.14 (60.17)	5.01 (5.01)	20.61 (20.64)	100	88
7.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ OH(o)	132	65.81 (65.80)	5.78 (5.80)	18.02 (18.06)	72	59
8.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ OH(m)	118	65.79 (65.80)	5.68 (5.80)	18.03 (18.06)	88	70
9.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ OH(p)	169	65.76 (65.80)	5.72 (5.80)	17.93 (18.06)	100	74
10.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ O	110	66.66 (66.66)	6.16 (6.17)	17.24 (17.28)	98	80
11.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ N(CH ₃) ₂	243	67.68 (67.65)	6.75 (6.82)	20.72 (20.77)	75	60
12.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₄ H ₉ O	260	63.29 (63.38)	5.61 (5.63)	19.68 (19.71)	67	64
13.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅ OHCH ₂ O	173	63.51 (63.52)	5.78 (5.88)	16.39 (16.47)	100	82
14.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅ OHBr	127	52.41 (52.45)	4.29 (4.37)	14.32 (14.39)	62	60
15.	H	C ₆ H ₅	221	60.54 (60.55)	6.43 (6.42)	25.59 (25.68)	92	83
16.	H	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (o)	232	50.12 (50.19)	4.88 (4.94)	26.59 (26.61)	80	67
17.	H	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (m)	119	50.17 (50.19)	4.86 (4.94)	26.60 (26.61)	74	60
18.	H	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (p)	246	50.21 (50.19)	4.97 (4.94)	26.31 (26.61)	35	48
19.	H	C ₆ H ₄ OH(o)	91	56.42 (56.41)	5.89 (5.98)	23.87 (23.93)	60	49
20.	H	C ₆ H ₅ OHBr	308	42.20 (42.18)	4.13 (4.15)	17.78 (17.89)	80	65
21.	H	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ OBr ₂	166	35.46 (35.48)	3.42 (3.44)	13.69 (13.79)	88	67
22.	H	C ₆ H ₄ N(CH ₃) ₂	256	59.77 (59.77)	7.27 (7.27)	26.81 (26.81)	63	49
23.	H	C ₆ H ₄ Cl	135	52.28 (52.27)	5.16 (5.14)	22.02 (22.17)	75	52
24.	H	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ O	164	58.13 (58.06)	6.49 (6.45)	22.49 (22.58)	80	69
25.	H	CH ₃	101	46.21 (46.15)	7.71 (7.69)	35.79 (35.89)	73	68
26.	H	C ₆ H ₅ OHCH ₂ O	174	54.51 (54.54)	6.13 (6.06)	21.11 (21.21)	70	62

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